

Nickel-Catalyzed Deoxycyanation of Activated Phenols via Cyanurate Intermediates with Zn(CN)₂: A Route to Aryl Nitriles

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Abstract

A novel, and efficient nickel-catalyzed deoxycyanation of phenolic compounds using relatively nontoxic Zn(CN)₂ as the cyanide source was developed. The reaction of C-O bond activated phenolic compounds by 2,4,6-trichloro-1,3,5-triazine with Zn(CN)₂ in the presence of a nickel precatalyst afforded the aromatic nitriles in good to excellent yields.